

Cognitively Inspired Automobiles: a new cooperative framework for addressing Autonomy in Teams

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Abstract

The design and development of autonomous systems – and autonomous vehicles (AVs) in particular – is mostly considered from an engineering perspective, without taking into account the mutual and comprehensive interaction between the human-agent and the machine-agent. Inside the AutoMate project, we propose to apply methods from the AI research to allow for a reasonable situation evaluation and behavior generation, with the goal to mimic human capabilities, in order to ensure that the system is able to cope with events not foreseeable in the design phase and – above all – also to ensure that the behavior of AVs is easily and intuitively understandable, as well as that their actions are predictable, by all humans interacting with these systems (these vehicles have always to interact with not automated systems, e.g. pedestrians).

1 Introduction

A number of intelligent agents is entering our lives and supporting us in a wider variety of tasks; in particular, this is definitely true for automotive domain, where automation in passenger cars is constantly increasing. In fact, current roadmaps of car-manufacturers and suppliers predict automated vehicles on highways by 2020. The reasons for that are threefold (from AdaptIVe project: <https://www.adaptive-ip.eu/>): *Zero Emission* (e.g. reduction of fuel consumption and CO2 emission); *Demographic Change* (e.g. enhancement of mobility for elderly people); *Vision Zero* (that is, more support to driver, by avoiding human errors).

In particular for the last point, automation can prevent human errors and supports human drivers because of: precise and fast perception as well as information integration; risk assessment; precise action execution. This trend has been already started with the introduction of the so-called advanced driving support systems (ADAS) which have been proved to have a positive effects both on traffic flow efficiency and traffic safety (see [Kessler et al, 2012] [Van Arem et al., 2006]). On the other hand, we have also to consider that accidents are rare events: one accident per 1.46 Billion km [Vorndran, 2010]. This means that – overall – humans are reliable, with the capacity to handle complex and new situations, have great capability of adaptation as well as of situation comprehension and anticipation.

Therefore, humans will remain part of the system for a long time. In fact, automation cannot cope with highly complex traffic situations, e.g. dense urban traffic. The situation understanding and prediction capabilities of vehicles are at the moment far less sophisticated than the capabilities of human drivers. Consequently, the automation is clearly overburdened in complex and unexpected situations (i.e. if other traffic participants operate against traffic rules) and will need the support of the driver. In fact, among the most fascinating capabilities of intelligent beings is the seamless perception and interaction with their environment, as well as the possibility to learn from experience.

Given this context, the question of how these autonomous agents (the automated vehicle and the human driver) can interact each other in a simple and natural way becomes of paramount importance and this will require that agents are able to learn when to support and how to mediate joint actions in a collaboration. The European project AutoMate (<http://www.automate-project.eu/>) addresses these topics, in which mixed teams of humans and artificial agents have to operate in collaborative settings. Our long term vision is that automated cooperation among traffic participants can improve traffic efficiency and safety beyond the level attainable by only human drivers or only machine-agents. In details, the top-level objective of AutoMate is to develop, evaluate and demonstrate the “TeamMate Car” concept as a major enabler of highly automated vehicles, considering the possibility to mimic the learning capability of humans, which is one of the most ambitious goals of automatic learning systems. This concept regards driver and automation as members of one team that understand and support each other in pursuing cooperatively the goal of driving safely, efficiently and comfortably from A to B.

Thus, the goal of this paper is to describe the project activity (AutoMate has a duration of 36 months and currently it is in the middle of its development phase) with the specific focus on the interactive framework between an artificial driver agent and a human driver agent, that cooperate to accomplish the driving task.

2 Definition of the Framework

Current automated systems (e.g. “Google Car”) are “programmed to follow the letter of the law” and it is one of the greatest development challenges to blend them into a world in which humans show a much more flexible behaviour not always behaving by the book, also considering that for a

substantial period of time there will be a mixture of cars with varying degrees of automation on the road (ranging from no automation to highly and fully automated vehicles). In addition, drivers of less automated vehicles need to interact with automated vehicles. Thus, the question for successful human-machine interaction design is: “how to turn automated systems into effective team players”?

A crucial aspect is the trust and the transparency in decision making; this depends on how well the agents interact, communicate and cooperate with humans both inside and outside the vehicle. In fact, this quality of cooperation and communication will strongly determine the driver’s trust in the automated systems. Our proposal is enhance safety by using the strength of both the automation and human driver in a dynamic situation dependent way. The automation is understood and designed as the driver’s companion or teammate.

2.1 The Driving Task

The driving task is a complex interplay of several sub-tasks that must be executed in a coordinated way to ensure safe, efficient and comfortable driving. According to several frameworks, the driving task can be regarded as a hierarchy of different levels, each level addressing specific tasks.

Figure 1: the layered architecture for the driving task, as used in the *AutoMate* project.

In order to describe the different control tasks that human and machine have to perform as a joint cognitive system, we have adopted the extended control model (ECOM) [Hollnagel, 2000] because it allows a decomposition in parallel behaviors (hierarchical levels of competence) and, moreover, because it is multi-goal, multi-sensor (perceptual synthesis), robust, scalable, each level includes sub-level competences. So, for example, the *targeting level* refers to long term goals and psychological states (e.g., go home quickly), while the *monitoring level* is about the short term goals and driving styles (e.g. overtake “a” instead of “b”). Then, there is the *regulating level*, which comprehends the Space-Time Trajectories (i.e., including speed). Finally, the *tracking level* considers the vehicle control. Here, it is not important who is performing what, but that a given task is

performed. So, in different scenarios, different tasks and different control loops are dynamically allocated between driver and (TeamMate) car.

In order to model the artificial agent, we have considered the following cognitive architecture:

Figure 2: cognitive architecture to model the artificial agent, following the Hollnagel scheme.

In the following paragraph we consider the system perspective and architecture as it is implemented in the project.

2.2 Driver-Vehicle Cooperation

Based on its perceptual capabilities (including algorithms for data fusion, situation interpretation, etc.), the TeamMate Car can collect information from its surrounding, in order to construct an environment and situation model on its own. Based on this representation of the environment and of the situation, the TeamMate Car is able to generate and evaluate possible action plans in the background parallel to the driver’s actions, decisions and planning. Thus, it can make decisions and execute these plans, even taking over the control of some driving subtasks or the complete driving task in certain situations. Therefore, driver and vehicle have to be regarded as a joint system rather than two separate systems and this joint system has to perform all relevant driving tasks to achieve a safe and efficient driving. The following figure provides a scheme for the task distribution in a joint-vehicle system:

Figure 3: concept of driver-vehicle cooperation, where tasks, agents and resources are shown. It is important to highlight that the allocation of both tasks and resources is dynamic, since it can

change time-by-time, depending on the external situation and on the agents conditions and states.

At any given moment in time, all relevant subtasks are carried out by the joint system. Consequently, the distribution of subtasks between the human driver and the TeamMate Car must not possess any gaps, leaving some subtasks unattended. On the other hand, some overlaps in task distribution are unavoidable and in some cases absolute necessary. For example, the vehicle always collects information from the environment, as well as it builds and updates its environment and situation model based on the collected data, independent on the fact whether the human driver also attends to the driving situation or he/she is occupied with a driving irrelevant task, such as reading emails. This is the only way to efficiently create a shared situation representation as the basis for communication between the human driver and the TeamMate Car.

In addition, the distribution of tasks within the joint driver-vehicle system needs to be dynamic due to the fact that the joint driver-vehicle system is faced with a situation that can change without any action from the driver or automation. This implies that one of the agent of the team can be overloaded or the limits are surpassed, thus a redistribution of tasks has to be carried out, so that a safe state is guaranteed. For example, this is one of the use-cases (UCs) addressed in the project, showing the following story. Peter is driving in a narrow rural road in Automated Mode. The car, arriving behind a tractor, detects that it obstructs the view. Therefore, the vehicle is not confident to overtake as its sensors are blocked by the tractor and it cannot perceive the opposite lane far enough to exclude oncoming traffic. Without any cooperation, as it is nowadays, the vehicle would follow the tractor either until it can perceive the road far enough or the tractor changes direction. Clearly, this is not an “optimal” solution (the “TM Car knows” that he prefers overtaking in similar situations), so the TeamMate car asks Peter to check if it is safe to overtake. When Peter confirms, the TeamMate car overtakes in Automated Mode. So, in different scenarios, different tasks and different control loops are dynamically allocated between driver and (TeamMate) car. In this example of Peter’s use-case, with reference to the ECOM illustration of figure 1, all control loops are performed by the TeamMate besides, for a short moment in time, the Targeting Loop, as the driver assess the current situation, sets the actual goal - namely perform overtaking manoeuvre. This leads then to updated values on the lower control levels / loops.

3 Implementation of the TeamMate Concept

In this context, humans and machines execute tasks together, use resources together, interact with each other in a dynamic environment and make autonomous decisions. But the question is: “who does what and when”? “How they cooperate and how much this cooperation is effective”? Following the Hoc’s framework [Hoc’s 2002], we assume that the cooperation modes are not a fixed characteristic but they need to adapt and change dynamically, depending on the

situation, the current state of the human and of the machine. In our layered architecture – illustrated in Section 2 – we can distinguish three levels of cooperation based on the level of the driving task, where the interaction between driver and automation takes place [Hoc et al. (2009)]. At the lowest level there is “*cooperation in action*”, where the cooperation is directly related to the control actions necessary for longitudinal and lateral control. The second level is “*cooperation in planning*”. Cooperation at this level mainly addresses activities and goals at the manoeuvre level of the driving task. For successful cooperation at this level, the maintenance of a shared situation representation is highly important as human driver and automation have to agree on and make decisions about the upcoming manoeuvres what requires an adequate and correct representation of the environment as well as the cooperating partners’ goals and plans. The third so-called “meta-level” involves maintaining long-term models of the partners, based on the experience and training. In the example of Peter (paragraph 2.2), we have showed a cooperation in perception/planning; another possibility is the cooperation in action, where the interaction between human and automation occurs through the shared control: e.g. the vehicle takes care of the longitudinal task, while the human driver takes the responsibility of the lateral control.

3.1 Concept Architecture

The concept of driver-automation teams is illustrated as following:

Figure 4: TeamMate concept of driver-automation team.

This figure 4 shows the main building blocks of the TeamMate Car architecture: TeamMate system, automated driving functions (like automated overtaking), and the vehicle. The TeamMate System manages the automated functions according to the needs of the situation and the driver, taking also into account the system constraints. It performs a cycle involving several steps:

- track & assess the situational states, capabilities, limitations and information demand of both driver and automation (left part of the figure);
- plan safe maneuvers considering all these factors;
- distribute the shared maneuver execution to driver and automation, including handing-over tasks to

the driver or accepting/rejecting tasks assigned by the driver to the automation;

- “explain” maneuvers, situation & task distribution to the driver;
- execute maneuvers in a human-like way, which feels natural and comfortable for the driver as well as for drivers in other cars;
- learn from the driver how to drive human-like, by observing the driver and adopting her/his manual behavior if it assessed to be safe;
- ask for information and even for decisions.

All communication takes driver’s situational awareness into account to prevent annoying the driver, consequently the HMI provides only information that is not yet known.

3.2 System Architecture

In the current stage of the project, the demonstrators vehicles are building, considering the following architectural scheme:

Figure 5: prototype vehicle system architecture.

This system architecture has been defined in the AutoMate project and it will be used to build the TeamMate car demonstrators (despite the fact they are real-vehicles or driving simulators) and it can be re-used after the project completion to implement highly automated systems with sophisticated human-machine cooperation capabilities. The central point for any driver assistance systems – and even more for autonomous systems – is the ability to assess perception and decision performance under a given condition in a certain situation. With reference to the perception-cognition-decision process, as defined in [Stiller et al., 2007], input is received from sensors (considering several aspects and sources, e.g. internal camera for gestures and eye movements, from maps, from the environment and so on) over several processing steps via a geometrical-symbolic representation of the current traffic environment to the generation and control of suitable behavior. In this context, robustness is essential: one successful method to obtain it is to consider data-fusion from several sensors. This may happen on a sub-symbolic or symbolic level, in order to

generate more robust hypothesis. Thereby, it is crucial to not only propagate knowledge through the cognition scheme but to augment this knowledge with confidence measures, which are consistently processed at each step of the cognition chain, considering the confidence of previous processing steps along with additional noise introduced by sensors and the uncertainty introduced by the individual algorithms. In our architectural scheme, there are software components for each Enabler linked with each other according to three main functional steps: data fusion, model driven assessment, as well as anticipation and planning. Output is delivered to the driver (either visual, acoustic, or haptic), the automation subsystems and the vehicle.

Among the enablers developed by the project, two are worth to be mentioned here: the **Driver Distraction Classifier** (DDC) and the **Driver Intention Recognition** (DIR). Since distraction is a critical human factor with significant safety concerns [Regan et al., 2011], we have developed a visual distraction classifier, based on the Machine Learning approach. Driver intention recognition is mainly concerned with the recognition of maneuver (e.g. lane change, overtaking, etc.) intentions. Due to the sound foundation of machine-learning methods and the direct interpretability of their structure and parameters, we used Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBNs) for modeling driver intention recognition used in the AutoMate project. Both these models are used to change the strategies of Autonomous Driving (AD) accordingly, that is, taking into account if the driver is attentive or not, as well as which are his/her intentions (and from that, his/her preferences). In particular, with reference to the example in Section 2, DIR module allows the TM Car to understand that Peter would like to overtake the tractor on rural road and thus the car can anticipate the request.

3.3 TeamMate Car in Action

As aforementioned in the previous sections, both the human and the automation have limits that can negatively affect the safety as well as the efficiency, the comfort, the trust and the acceptance of the autonomous driving. For the human, the limits are often related to his/her driving performance: they are likely to affect the safety (e.g. distracted), and cause accidents. For the automation, the limits, mostly at perception and decision level, may affect the efficiency and the comfort of the trip, and then, in turn, the acceptance of the automation.

Therefore, the AutoMate approach is based on the mutual complementarity between the driver and the automation: this support is achieved through the cooperation between the team members:

Figure 6: schematic representation of the TeamMate concept.

While the Automation to Human support (A2H) is used to complement the human limits, the Human to Automation (H2A) is implemented to allow the driver to support the automation to overcome its limits. The complementarity between the driver and the automation is the conceptual solution to compensate the reciprocal limitations, while the cooperation is how the complementarity is implemented. In order to illustrate how it works, let's consider the following situation, that we named the *Eva scenario*. The TeamMate car is driving in Automated Mode. When it approaches a roundabout, it detects that may be not able to handle complex situations, either “efficiently” (i.e. because performing an “over-safe” maneuver, waiting until the roundabout is empty and thus causing possible relevant frustration to Eva) or “completely” (i.e. lanes not available and thus a safe behavior cannot be ensured). Nowadays, if the Automated Vehicle (AV) cannot be perform a safe maneuver, it simply sends a take-over request to the driver. In that case, TM car asks Eva for a cooperation in one of the following modes:

- *Perception/decision*: Eva checks the available space and the traffic, then provides a trigger to start the maneuver (giving the confirmation to enter the roundabout). The TM car understands the feedback and enters the roundabout in Automated Mode (lanes are present).
- *Action*: TM car proposes a shared control (e.g. lateral control to the driver, longitudinal control to the machine), if the car is not able to travel into the roundabout autonomously (i.e. no lanes on the road).

In addition, the system monitors also the Eva cognitive status: if she is detected as distracted, appropriate strategies to take her back into the control loop are considered, before asking for cooperation (and before entering into the roundabout).

The figure 7 shows the transitions states and the related conditions to move from one state to another. We can identify three main block: Manual Mode (MM), Automation (AU) or Automated Mode (AM) and Control Sharing (CS) or TeamMate mode.

In details, the MM includes both the manual driving (like a traditional pre-ADAS car) and an assisted modality, where the system supports the driver with warning, information and advice, such as nowadays ADAS application.

After that all the conditions are met (so, the system is *Ready*), the TM car is able to drive autonomously (AU). When the TM system needs the driver to supervise (or even intervene), asks for that (*Request*).

Finally, there is the Control Sharing Mode, in which several cooperation levels are possible with the system:

Figure 8: Driver-Vehicle Cooperation Framework according to [Hoc et al. (2009)].

As showed in the figure above, the following modes are considered: **Cooperation mode in action**, that means both agents (human and machine) are sharing the intervention task (e.g. driver is responsible for the lateral aspect, while the TM system of the longitudinal one); **Cooperation mode in planning**, that means the system delegates the final decision task to the human (e.g.: due to limited information); **Cooperation mode in perception**, that means the system can asks for support in the environment perception (e.g.: because of limitation in the perception aspects).

Like in nowadays AD systems, also in this case a Safe Mode (SM) state has been foreseen. If the driver is not responding or it is necessary an emergency shutdown of TM functionalities, the system enters in the SM. First, it tries to perform a minimum risk maneuver (e.g.: stop in the emergency lane), then – if not possible – in order to preserve the safety of the vehicle and its passengers, the vehicle is stopped in an automatic manner.

Figure 7: state-diagram of the TeamMate system for transitions.

4 Discussion, Conclusions and Perspectives

In the future, agents are expected to offer a broad range of support in different tasks. This will require that agents are able to learn when to support and how to mediate joint actions in a collaboration. In such a perspective, AutoMate focuses on how autonomous intelligent systems can successfully interact and shape each other's autonomy spaces (considering both the individual, specific goals and maybe one jointly overarching goal). To sum up, the project considers how can we build robots (vehicles, in our case) and virtual agents that successfully realize collaboration between humans and automated vehicles.

4.1 Impact of the TeamMate Technology

The Benefits of our TeamMate (TM) approach are the following (considering the examples illustrated in the previous sections, in particular the use-cases of Peter and Eva):

- the vehicle could reduce the time that is needed to enter the roundabout (and, as a consequence, the frustration of the driver).
- The support in perception/decision or in action is able to increase the effectiveness (i.e. the safety) of the trip.
- The cooperation is able to improve the comfort and the acceptance.
- The state of the driver is considered for appropriate cooperation request

Thus, the most relevant impacts of the TeamMate concept are in the area of shared control in collaborative human-vehicle tasks: we showed how the roles and the strategies can be divided between human-agents and machine-agents. Moreover, a fundamental aspect is the learning and modeling of human-agent interaction, human instructions and collaborative behavior. This will be done in the second period of the project (see next paragraphs), in order to enhance trust and transparency in decision making.

4.2 Final Remarks & future Perspectives

Within the collaborative European project AutoMate, the involved partners focus on the systematic and interdisciplinary research on machine cognition of autonomous systems, as a basis for a scientific theory of machine behavior. In particular, this workshop paper has presented a framework for the interaction and cooperation between human-agents and machine-agents, both regarded as members of a unique team (the joint driver-vehicle system).

Since AutoMate is still in the middle of its duration (36 months overall), no final integration and tests have been already done, but we foresee to start with the first experimental phases in the next months (from June 2018), in order to collect the data to be used for the first iteration of the TeamMate training, using an Markovian Decision Process (MDP) in combination with the Reinforcement Learning (RL) approach.

The issue is to find the optimal mapping between situations, constituting the perception part (described by physical variables, such as: speed, distance, etc.) and actions (represented by one of the final states of the AutoMate vehicle, such as stopping or passing a given position). This is a strategy, that can be regarded as a sequential decision making

problem, as decisions are taken one after the other (given their effects on the specific situation). In addition, it is a global strategy (not local decision) that the system has to optimize. The system (that is, the TeamMate car) can be modelled as an MDP and the answer to this sequential decision making optimization is RL paradigm [Puterman, 2005]. Here, an intelligent agent learns a control strategy by interacting with a system. The system is supposed to be made up of states and the control takes the form of actions performed on the system. As a consequence of each action, the system steps from one state to another and generates an immediate reward. This reward is visible to the agent whose goal is to learn a mapping from states to actions that maximizes some cumulative function of rewards. The agent then searches for the best sequence of actions and not for decisions that are locally optimal. A draft scheme for the implementation of the MDP using a RL approach is the following:

Figure 9: Implementation scheme for the TeamMate car

As sketched, this is an iteration design, where the artificial agent learns (the TeamMate system) to interact optimally with a stochastic dynamic system through direct interactions with human-agent: the goal is to learn an optimal interaction policy, that is, the motion planner that makes trajectories similar to human driver. This approach is envisaged to make autonomous driving system more acceptable (similar to humans) and hence more trustable and understandable by the surrounding traffic actors, independently on the fact they are other driverless vehicles or “normal” cars.

Finally, during these experiments, another relevant and interesting aspects will be considered and investigated. In fact, from one hand we have the learning of AV from the human behavior (of course taking into account all the safety issues and, thus, avoiding any risky actions), from the other hand, there is also the learning of human drivers from the system, adapting and maybe changing their own driving style.

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